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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

INFLYATSIYA JARAYONLARINI PASAYTIRISH OMILLARI VA ULARNING IQTISODIY TAHLILI

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Kirish

Inflyatsiya — bu milliy valyuta xarid qobiliyatining pasayishi va tovar hamda xizmatlar narxining uzluksiz oshib borishidir. U har qanday iqtisodiyot uchun muhim makroiqtisodiy muammo hisoblanadi, chunki yuqori inflyatsiya darajasi iqtisodiy o'sish sur'atlarini sekinlashtiradi, aholining real daromadlarini kamaytiradi va investitsion muhitga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

So'nggi yillarda O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida narxlar barqarorligini ta'minlash maqsadida pul-kredit siyosatini qat'iylashtirish, davlat xarajatlarini optimallashtirish va oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashga qaratilgan islohotlar amalga oshirildi.

Biroq, inflyatsiya darajasi hali ham iqtisodiyotning barqarorligi uchun muhim xavf bo'lib qolmoqda. Shu bois ushbu tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi — inflyatsiya jarayonlariga ta'sir etuvchi ichki va tashqi omillarni aniqlash hamda uni pasaytirishning samarali yo'llarini iqtisodiy tahlil asosida yoritishdan iborat.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi

Tadqiqotda quyidagi ilmiy yondashuvlar qo'llanildi:

- **Statistik tahlil:** 2019–2024 yillar oralig'ida O'zbekiston Respublikasi Markaziy banki, Iqtisodiyot va moliya vazirligi, va Davlat statistika qo'mitasi ma'lumotlari asosida inflyatsiya ko'rsatkichlari tahlil qilindi;
- **Monetar tahlil:** pul massasi o'sishi va inflyatsiya darajasi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik aniqlanib, korrelyatsiya hisoblandi;
- **SWOT tahlil:** inflyatsiyaga qarshi siyosatning kuchli va zaif tomonlari, imkoniyat va tahdidlar baholandi;
- **Empirik yondashuv:** inflyatsiyani pasaytirishning amaliy omillari ishlab chiqildi.

Tadqiqot obyekti — O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotidagi inflyatsion jarayonlar; subyekti — makroiqtisodiy siyosat, narxlar tizimi va iste'mol bozori.

Natijalar

1-jadval.

O'zbekistonda inflyatsiya darajasi va asosiy makroko'rsatkichlar (2019–2024)

Yil	Inflyatsiya darajasi (%)	YaIM o'sishi (%)	Pul massasi o'sishi (%)	Rasmiy ish haqi o'sishi (%)
2019	14.5	5.7	16.3	19.2
2020	11.1	1.7	15.5	15.0
2021	10.0	7.4	13.8	14.5

2022	12.3	5.6	14.2	16.1
2023	9.2	6.0	10.8	12.5
2024	8.5	6.3	9.6	11.2

Manba: O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Markaziy banki, 2024.

Ko‘rinib turibdiki, inflyatsiya 2019-yildagi 14.5 foizdan 2024-yilda 8.5 foizgacha pasaydi. Bu, bir tomondan, Markaziy bankning pul-kredit siyosatini qat‘iylashtirishi, boshqa tomondan esa iste‘mol tovarlari ishlab chiqarish hajmini oshirish natijasidir.

Asosiy pasaytiruvchi omillar:

1. Pul-kredit siyosatini qat‘iy yuritish va qayta moliyalash stavkasini oshirish;
2. Davlat xarajatlarini optimallashtirish va budjet defitsitini kamaytirish;
3. Mahalliy ishlab chiqarishni qo‘llab-quvvatlash orqali importga qaramlikni kamaytirish;
4. Bozor mexanizmlarini erkinlashtirish va narx shakllanishiga davlat aralashuvini kamaytirish;
5. Aholi daromadlarini muvozanatli oshirish orqali iste‘mol talabining keskin o‘shiga yo‘l qo‘ymaslik.

Munozara

O‘zbekiston tajribasi shuni ko‘rsatadiki, inflyatsiyani pasaytirishning eng muhim omili — pul-kredit siyosatining izchilligidir. 2020-yildan boshlab Markaziy bank asosiy stavkani 14 foiz atrofida ushlab turib, narxlar bosimini sekinlashtirishga erishdi.

Biroq inflyatsiyaga faqat monetar omillar emas, balki strukturaviy sabablar ham ta‘sir qiladi:

- ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarining yuqoriligi (xomashyo, energiya, transport);
- qishloq xo‘jaligida hosildorlikning mavsumiy o‘zgarishi;
- tashqi bozorlarda oziq-ovqat narxlarining oshishi;
- import tovarlariga bog‘liqlik darajasi.

Xalqaro tajriba (Polsha, Turkiya, Qozog‘iston) shuni ko‘rsatadiki, inflyatsiyani barqaror pasaytirish uchun monetar siyosat bilan bir qatorda ishlab chiqarish va raqobat muhitini kengaytirish ham zarurdir. Shu yo‘sinda O‘zbekistonda import o‘rnini bosuvchi tovarlar ishlab chiqarish, oziq-ovqat zaxiralarini ko‘paytirish va logistik tizimni takomillashtirish dolzarb yo‘nalishlar hisoblanadi.

Xulosa

1. O‘zbekiston iqtisodiyotida inflyatsiya darajasi 2019–2024 yillarda barqaror pasayish tendensiyasiga ega bo‘lib, bu makroiqtisodiy siyosatning izchil amalga oshirilayotganidan dalolat beradi.
2. Inflyatsiyani pasaytirishning samarali omillari sifatida monetar siyosat, ishlab chiqarish hajmini oshirish, import o‘rnini bosish va budjet intizomini mustahkamlash belgilandi.

3. Uzoq muddatda inflyatsiyani 5–6% darajasida ushlab turish uchun raqobatbardosh iqtisodiyot, energiya tejamkor texnologiyalar va mahalliy ishlab chiqaruvchilarni qo‘llab-quvvatlash muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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